

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Agricultural management affects active carbon and nitrogen mineralisation potential in soils

Sophia Hendricks¹ | Sophie Zechmeister-Boltenstern² | Ellen Kandeler³ |
 Taru Sandén¹ | Eugenio Diaz-Pines² | Jörg Schnecker⁴ | Oliver Alber⁵ |
 Julia Miloczki¹ | Heide Spiegel¹

¹Department for Soil Health and Plant Nutrition, Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), Wien, Austria

²Department of Forest- and Soil Sciences, Institute of Soil Research, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Wien, Austria

³Institute of Soil Science and Land Evaluation, Soil Biology Department, University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart, Germany

⁴Department of Microbiology and Ecosystem Science, University of Vienna, Wien, Austria

⁵Institute for Statistics and Analytical Epidemiology, Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), Graz, Austria

Correspondence

Sophia Hendricks, Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), Department for Soil Health and Plant Nutrition, Spargelfeldstrasse 191, Wien 1220, Austria.

Email: sophiahendricks@gmx.de

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Abstract

Background: Soil organic matter (SOM) is important for soil fertility and climate change mitigation. Agricultural management can improve soil fertility and contribute to climate change mitigation by stabilising carbon in soils. This calls for cost-effective parameters to assess the influence of management practices on SOM contents.

Aims: The current study aimed at understanding how sensitively the parameters active carbon (AC) and nitrogen mineralisation potential (NMP) react to different agricultural management practices compared to total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (N_t). We aimed to gain a better understanding of SOM processes, mainly regarding depth distribution and seasonality of SOM dynamics using AC and NMP.

Methods: We looked mainly at four parameters, namely permanganate oxidisable carbon (AC), nitrogen mineralisation potential (NMP), total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (N_t). Data were obtained in five long-term field experiments (LTEs) testing four management practices: (1) tillage, (2) compost application, (3) crop residue management, and (4) mineral fertilization.

Results: AC was specifically sensitive in detecting the effect of tillage treatment at different soil depths. NMP differentiated between all different tillage treatments in the upper soil layer, it showed the temporal dynamics between the years in the compost LTE, and it was identified as an early detection property in the crop residue LTE. Both AC and NMP detected short-term fluctuations better than TOC and N_t over the course of two years in the crop residue LTE.

Conclusion: We suggest that AC and NMP are two valuable soil biochemical parameters providing more detailed information on C and N dynamics regarding depth distribution and seasonal dynamics and react more sensitively to different agricultural management practices compared to TOC and N_t . They should be integrated in monitoring agricultural long-term experiments (LTEs) and in field analyses conducted by farmers. However, when

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evaluating results towards long-term carbon storage, their sensitivity toward annual fluctuations should be taken into account.

KEYWORDS

agricultural long-term experiments, climate change mitigation, early parameters of change, soil organic matter

1 | INTRODUCTION

Soil organic matter (SOM) plays a central role in soil health (Lehmann et al., 2020; Wade et al., 2020). SOM can increase the cation exchange capacity (CEC), improve soil structure through aggregation and is a nutrient and energy source for plants and soil microbes (Amelung et al., 2018; Krull et al., 2004). Soil quality refers to the ability of a soil to fulfil functions including primary productivity, water regulation and purification, as well as nutrient cycling in a natural or managed ecosystem. SOM is one parameter defining soil quality, which can be improved by adapted management (Amelung et al., 2018). To understand processes related to mineralization and nutrient availability in soils, it is essential to quantify SOM fractions, with special focus on organic C and N pools (Kaur et al., 2008). Soil organic carbon (SOC) has an important function in the global carbon cycle because 80% of the terrestrial organic C stocks are in the soil (Amelung et al., 2018). The distinction between SOC fractions and the separation of SOC pools with different turnover rates is important to comprehend SOM stabilization and decomposition processes (Poepflau, Don et al., 2018). Moreover, N pools must be considered when analyzing SOM decomposition processes and long-term carbon storage (Van Groenigen et al., 2017).

Agriculture is responsible for a distinct amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and there is great pressure on farmers to mitigate them (Arbuckle Jr et al., 2015). Shifting from conventional agricultural production to alternative management practices, such as reduced tillage, compost application and crop residue incorporation, has a positive effect on different C and N pools in soil (Awale et al., 2017; Bongiorno et al., 2019; Charoulis et al., 2005; Chowdhury et al., 2015; Diacono & Montemurro, 2011; Gajda & Przewloka, 2012; Neugschwandtner et al., 2014; Pecio & Jarosz, 2016; Spiegel et al., 2018) and can therefore benefit soil quality and productivity (Sandén et al., 2018). Long-term field experiments (LTE) provide valuable evidence in finding promising future management practices (Sandén et al., 2018). Small changes due to altered agricultural management, for example, SOC stock changes, can accumulate over time and become measurable. Accordingly, LTEs should ideally cover a period of at least 20 years (Leigh & Johnston, 1994; Zavattaro et al., 2015). A large body of research has examined the effect of agricultural management on SOC pools (Awale et al., 2017; Benbi et al., 2015; Bolinder et al., 2020; Bongiorno et al., 2019; Haddaway et al., 2015), but many questions remain regarding the effect of management practices such as reduced tillage, organic amendments and N fertilization on SOC storage (Chenu et al., 2019).

Cotrufo et al. (2013) proposed that labile compounds contribute even more to long-term SOM storage than, for example, lignin-rich, recalcitrant material. Microbes use labile C sources more efficiently

than more stable and primarily recalcitrant parts (Qiao et al., 2019). Microbial necromass originating from labile plant parts could therefore be the main contributor to stable SOM (Miltner et al., 2012) because of more efficient microbial utilization (Qiao et al., 2019). Moreover, microbes promote aggregation and bind strongly to the mineral soil matrix (Cotrufo et al., 2013). Labile SOM fractions are important for soil fertility, aggregate stability and soil biodiversity and may indicate a change in soil quality rather soon after changes in management practices (Chenu, et al., 2019). Weil et al. (2003) developed a method to determine a labile fraction after KMnO_4 extraction. Tatzber et al. (2015) modified the method for estimating the permanganate oxidizable carbon component, here referred to as active carbon (AC), with an alternative titration procedure to make it suitable for routine laboratory analysis. The aim was to better characterize the labile soil carbon fraction (Dell, 2009; Tatzber et al., 2015). Culman et al. (2012) reported that AC is a relatively processed pool of labile soil carbon because it correlated more strongly with smaller than larger particulate organic carbon (POC) fractions and had a closer relationship to heavier than lighter POC fractions. This would make AC a good parameter indicating SOM stabilization and long-term storage (Hurisso et al., 2016)—an important aspect in the discussion around climate change adaption and mitigation. However, there are also studies suggesting that KMnO_4 not necessarily dissolves a labile pool, or even correlates with lignin (Tirol-Padre & Ladha, 2004; Romero et al., 2018). Therefore, there is a huge knowledge gap on the actual fraction identified by the KMnO_4 method. According to Tatzber et al. (2015), AC can provide reproducible and reliable results; it was more sensitive than total organic carbon (TOC) towards different tillage variants and cropping systems. In Culman et al. (2012), AC reacted stronger to tillage type, fertilization, depth, time and other factors in comparison to POC, microbial biomass carbon (MBC) or TOC. AC is generally reported to be a relatively marginally applied method with great potential for identifying labile soil carbon because it is considered to be sensitive to management changes and is both rapid and inexpensive (Culman et al., 2012; Weil et al., 2003). Moreover, as mentioned by Weil et al. (2003) and Mandal et al. (2011), measuring AC could be simplified to enable farmers to quantify this labile carbon fraction directly on the field, further increasing the potential of this parameter. Nonetheless, a knowledge gap remains on the sensitivity of AC to changing management practices compared to other SOC parameters (Culman et al., 2012).

It is also essential to analyze N pools when investigating SOM processes and storage in soil (Van Groenigen et al., 2017). Nitrogen mineralization potential (NMP), identified using the anaerobic incubation method (Dersch et al., 2003; Keeney, 1983; Schinner et al., 1991), indicate easily mineralizable compounds (Drinkwater et al., 1997). It depicts SOM that is decomposed and releases N relatively quickly

TABLE 1 Site description of the five investigated AGES (Austrian Agency for Health & Food Safety) long-term field experiments (LTEs), located at three regions in Austria (Marchfeld: Crop residue and tillage LTE; Alpenvorland: Crop residue and mineral fertilization LTE; Oberösterreich: Compost LTE)

Region LTE	Marchfeld		Alpenvorland		Oberösterreich
	Tillage LTE	Crop residue LTE - Rutzendorf	Crop residue LTE - Alpenvorland	Mineral fertilization LTE	Compost LTE
GPS coordinates	48° 11' N 16° 44' E	48° 21' N 16° 61' E	48° 12' N 15° 15' E	48° 07' N 15° 13' E	48° 18' N 14° 25' E
ILTER site name	LTER_EU_AT_030	LTER_EU_AT_030	LTER_EU_AT_038		
Year established	1988	1982	1986	1973	1991
Soil type (WRB, 2015)	Haplic Chernosem	Calcaric Phaeozem	Gleyic Luvisol	Gleyic Luvisol	Cambisol
MAT	9.4°C	9.1°C	8.5°C	8.5°C	8.5°C
MAP	529 mm	540 mm	836 mm	836 mm	753 mm
Texture (% clay/silt/sand)	22/41/37	23/52/26	16/77/7	15/58/27	17/69/14
pH (CaCl ₂)	7.6	7.5	6.6	6.6	6.8
SOC	1.2%	2.2%	1.0%	1.0%	1.2%
Management treatments	Minimum tillage (MT); Reduced tillage (RT); Conventional tillage (CT)	Incorporation of crop residues; removal of crop residues	Incorporation of crop residues; removal of crop residues	Mineral fertilization with different stages of N-, P-, K- and Mg fertilization (70, 95, 120 and 145 kg N ha ⁻¹ ; 0, 24, 48 and 96 kg P ha ⁻¹ ; 0, 75, 149 and 299 kg K ha ⁻¹ ; 0, 30 and 60 kg Mg ha ⁻¹)	Mineral fertilization (0, 40, 80 or 120 kg N ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹); Compost amendments (bio-waste, green waste, manure or sewage sludge compost corresponding to 175 kg N ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ and 525 kg N ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹); Combination of compost and mineral fertilization (compost with additional 80 kg mineral N ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)
Sources	(Spiegel et al., 2007)	(Spiegel et al., 2018)	(Spiegel et al., 2018)	-	(Lehtinen et al., 2017)

(within a few years) under optimum soil temperature and soil moisture conditions (Nendel et al., 2019). Different authors have shown that NMP is a management-sensitive parameter towards tillage, crop sequence and liming (Kandeler, Tscherko et al., 1999; Soon et al., 2007). Furthermore, information on NMP can be used to improve fertilization because, with high NMP, reduced N-fertilization is recommended, for example in Austria (BMLFUW, 2017).

The current study was designed to investigate how sensitively the parameters active carbon (AC) and nitrogen mineralization potential (NMP) react to different agricultural management practices, namely (1) reduced tillage, (2) compost application, (3) crop residue management, and (4) mineral fertilization, compared to TOC and total nitrogen (N_t).

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Experimental set up

The experimental sites are described in Table 1.

2.1.1 | Tillage LTE

The ongoing tillage LTE was set up in 1988 in Fuchsenbigl, Lower Austria (Marchfeld), to determine the effects of different tillage practices

on chemical, physical and biological soil parameters and plants. The experiment has already been introduced in the literature (Franko & Spiegel, 2016; Kandeler & Böhm, 1996; Kandeler, Palli, et al., 1999; Kandeler, Tscherko et al., 1999; Spiegel et al., 2007). The crop rotation included the most common crops for the Marchfeld, i.e., cereals (e.g., winter wheat [*Triticum aestivum* L.]), sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* subsp. *vulgaris* L.), maize (*Zea mays* L.) and grain legumes (e.g., *Pisum sativum* L.). The experiment was structured as a randomized block design containing three replicates with a plot size of 720 m² (60 m × 12 m). In order to test the influence of different tillage management, the following treatments were applied: (1) minimum tillage (MT) with a rotary driller to a depth of 5–8 cm, (2) reduced tillage (RT) with a cultivator to a depth of 15–20 cm, and (3) conventional tillage (CT) with mouldboard ploughing to 25–30 cm (Spiegel et al., 2007).

2.1.2 | Compost amendments LTE

The ongoing LTE in Ritzlhof, close to Linz, Austria, was established in 1991. The soil, site and the treatments were explained by Ros et al. (2006), Tatzber et al. (2015) and Lehtinen et al. (2017). The experiment consisted of 16 treatments: One control treatment with no N fertilization at all, three stages of mineral N fertilization, four different compost amendments (urban organic waste compost, green waste

compost, cattle manure compost and sewage sludge compost), each corresponding to 175 kg N ha⁻¹ and 525 kg N ha⁻¹, and four compost treatments (175 kg N ha⁻¹) supplemented with 80 kg mineral N ha⁻¹. In the current study treatments were concised into five groups: control, mineral, organic 175 N, organic 175 N-mineral and organic 525 N. The crop rotation consisted of spring and winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), winter barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), maize (*Zea mays* L.) and field pea (*Pisum sativum* L.), the latter without compost or mineral fertilizer application (Lehtinen et al., 2017; Tatzber et al., 2015). Fertilizers were applied together with seedbed preparation after ploughing in autumn (winter barley and winter wheat) or in spring (spring wheat and maize). Cultivated crops in 2010, 2012, 2015 and 2018 were winter barley, pea, grain maize and again grain maize, respectively. There was no compost application in 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016 and 2017. Fertilizer was incorporated in the upper 10–15 cm with a rotary harrow and sowing was done afterwards. For the control and mineral treatments, additional 75 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ and 150 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ were applied. Mineral N fertilization for cereals was applied in different stages. The experiment is structured in a randomized design with 16 treatments, each with four replicates. The plot size is 30 m² with a 0.5 m buffer between plots.

2.1.3 | Crop residue management LTEs

The ongoing LTEs testing the impact of alternative crop residue management, incorporation or removal, combined with P-fertilization on SOM and nutrient dynamics were conducted at two experimental sites: (1) Marchfeld, Austria, since 1982, and (2) Alpenvorland, Austria, since 1986. More information on the crop residue LTE can be found in Lehtinen et al. (2014) and Spiegel et al. (2018). The crop rotations varied, but included the most important crops for the two regions (Spiegel et al., 2018); in more detail, at both sites winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) was cultivated in 2002 and 2012, winter barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) in 2010, spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) in 2014, grain maize (*Zea mays* L.) in 2016, spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) in 2018 and winter barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) in 2019. The field experiment was set up in a randomized block design with four replicates. In Marchfeld, each plot had a size of 192 m² (32 m × 6 m) and in Alpenvorland each plot was 225 m² (30 m × 7.5 m). At both sites, crop residues were either incorporated or removed. Furthermore, each crop residue treatment consisted of four P-fertilization stages (0, 33, 66 and 131 kg P ha⁻¹ y⁻¹).

2.1.4 | Mineral fertilization LTE

The LTE was established in 1973 in Zinsenhof, Lower Austria, to study the effects of increasing N-, P-, K- and Mg-fertilization levels in order to derive appropriate fertilization amounts according to the crop's need. In 2015, winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) and in 2018 spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) was grown. N was applied as NH₄NO₃, P as triple superphosphate (45% P), K as potassium chloride (60% K) and Mg as kieserite (27% MgO). The P-, K- and Mg-fertilization was conducted every second year since 1998 (it was applied in 2018, but not

in 2015). Harvest residues (straw, beet leaf, etc.) were always removed until 1991; thereafter they were usually incorporated. The LTE consists of 12 treatments with different stages of mineral N-, P-, K- and Mg-fertilization, replicated three times (= 36 plots). The size of each plot is 50 m² (10 m × 5 m). The experiment consists of four N stages (70, 95, 120, 145 kg N ha⁻¹), four P stages (0, 24, 48, 96 kg P ha⁻¹) and four K stages (0, 75, 149, 299 kg K ha⁻¹), whereas the main nutrients not tested are sufficiently available, respectively. In addition, there is a Mg series with 3 stages (0, 30, 60 kg Mg) with sufficient N, P and K supply.

2.2 | Soil sampling

On each LTE, soil samples were taken according to ÖNORM L 1055 (ÖNORM, 2004). Approximately 10 random soil cores from each treatment plot were collected and bulked. The samples were sieved to <2 mm, airdried and stored at air temperature prior to analyses. At the tillage LTE, soil sampling took place annually from 1998 to 2019 in spring (March/April) prior to fertilizer application. Soil samples were taken at depths of 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm. In 2013 and 2019, soil was additionally sampled in depths of 30–40, 40–60, 60–80, and 80–100 cm. At the compost amendments LTE, soil samples from 0–25 cm for the current study were taken in the years 2010, 2012, 2015 and 2018 after harvest. At the crop residue management LTEs, soil samples from 0–25 cm for the current study were taken after harvest in 2002, 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016 and 2018. In Alpenvorland, in the treatment plot where 66 kg P ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ was applied, soil samples were taken more frequently (02 July 2018, 01 August 2018, 13 August 2018, 17 September 2018, 06 November 2018, 19 November 2018, 17 December 2018, 28 January 2019, 11 March 2019, 29 April 2019, 15 June 2019 and 05 August 2019) over the course of 2 years from 0–5 cm depth at 12 dates, namely 2018 and 2019, to study seasonal dynamics of organic matter decomposition. Spring wheat and winter barley were cultivated in 2018 and 2019, respectively. At the mineral fertilization LTE, soil samples for the current study were taken in 2015 and 2018 after harvest at a depth of 0–25 cm.

2.3 | Analyses

2.3.1 | Soil analyses

Total organic carbon (TOC) in the soil samples was determined using dry combustion in a LECO RC-612 TruMac CN (LECO Corp., St Joseph, MI, USA) at 650°C (ÖNORM 1080). Elemental analysis using a CNS 2000 SGA-410-06 at 1250°C according to ÖNORM EN 16168 was used to investigate total N (N_t). Soil pH was analyzed electrochemically (pH/mV Pocket Meter pH 340i, WTW, Weilheim, Germany) in 0.01 M CaCl₂ at a soil-to-solution ratio of 1:5 (ÖNORM EN 15933).

Active carbon (AC) was determined with potassium permanganate (KMnO₄), with a titration of the 0.02M KMnO₄ solution with sodium oxalate (Na₂C₂O₄), according to Tatzber et al. (2015). The method was based on Weil et al. (2003) with modifications from other articles such as Culman et al. (2012). Those adaptations were made to create

a method suitable for fast and inexpensive routine laboratory analysis and for interlaboratory comparison. Briefly, 2.5 g air-dried soil sample were used and a volume of 20 mL 0.02 M KMnO₄ was added. Titration, needed because KMnO₄ is not a primary standard, was performed according to McBride (1912) and Jander et al. (1973) with Na₂C₂O₄ to avoid using the toxic arsenic trioxide (As₂O₃) as performed by Blair et al. (1995) in the same context. AC was measured from 2015 to 2019 in the tillage LTE; in 2018 in the compost LTE; and in 2014 and 2018 in the crop residue LTEs. For the latter LTE, AC was further measured seasonally in 2018 and 2019; in the mineral fertilization LTE no AC measurements were taken.

The anaerobic incubation method according to Keeney (1983), adapted by Kandeler in Schinner et al. (1991), was used to determine the nitrogen mineralisation potential (NMP) of dried soils. In Dersch et al. (2003) the method was modified for dry soils. Briefly, soil samples (5.0 g) were incubated at 40°C for 7 days in a waterlogged environment in a closed tube with little headspace. Released NH₄⁺ was measured colorimetrically.

2.3.2 | Statistical analyses

All analyses were conducted in the open-source statistic software R (version 3.4.4.) (R Core Team, 2017). Data were inspected with Shapiro–Wilk's test for normality. Normality of data was derived for all data. To analyse differences in soil parameters, for example, AC, TOC, between treatments in the individual field LTEs, we conducted two-way analyses of variance (two-way ANOVA) with treatment and replicate, treatment and time or treatment and depth as factors and subsequent Tukey's post hoc test for mean comparison. Two-way ANOVA with treatment and replicate as factors was performed in all sampling years for all experiments and in all depth levels for the tillage LTE (in 2019). Correlations between variables were calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient. Only sampling years in which both of the tested parameters were measured were included in the correlation analysis. Additionally, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed for all experiments. PCA creates new, uncorrelated variables which maximize variance (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016). Therefore, inspection of the first few compound axes shows which variables contribute the strongest to the differences between samples (Dytham, 2011). PCA was therefore used to determine how much variance of data could be explained by AC and NMP. Thus, correlations to principal component (PC) 1 and PC 2 were identified. Only sampling years in which AC measurements were performed and only the mainly investigated parameters—TOC, AC, N_t, NMP and pH—were used in the PCA. Furthermore, in the tillage LTE, only the depth 0–30 cm was used for the PCA and correlation calculations, except when correlations in different depths of the tillage LTE were compared. Plots and figures were created in R and in Microsoft Excel. To conduct the PCA we used the R package “vegan” (Oksanen et al., 2019). The significance level for all statistical analyses was defined as $p < 0.05$.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Tillage

In the tillage LTE, TOC, AC, N_t and NMP differed significantly across treatments in 2019, 31 years after the start of the LTE.

The three alternative tillage practices had a similar increasing effect on AC, TOC and N_t in the soil layer 0–10 cm in 2019.

AC and TOC were significantly increased in the 0–10 cm layer in MT when compared to both other treatments ($p = 0.002$, $p = 0.014$, respectively); RT and CT were not significantly different from each other (Figure 1A, B). AC was the only investigated parameter that showed differences between treatments in deeper soil depths. In depths 20–30 cm and 30–40 cm, the CT treatment was significantly enriched in AC when compared with RT and MT treatments ($p = 0.01$, $p = 0.027$, respectively). Thus, TOC and AC had lower levels at deeper depth under MT, while they were more equally depth-distributed under CT (to a depth of 40 cm). The decrease in AC to a depth of 40 cm was significant under MT ($p < 0.001$), but not under CT (data not shown), indicating that AC under CT did not decrease as abruptly with depth as under MT.

In the uppermost soil layer, NMP was highest in MT, followed by RT and CT (Figure 1D; $p = 0.001$). N_t, in contrast, had similar values for RT and CT, but was significantly higher under MT than in the other treatments (Figure 1C) ($p = 0.003$). In deeper soil layers, no significant differences between tillage treatments were found for N_t and NMP. For NMP, differences between upper soil layers (down to 40 cm) were significant under MT ($p < 0.001$), but not under CT (data not shown).

At 0–30 cm a strong, positive and significant correlation between NMP and AC was found for MT and RT when combining data of all sampling years (per variant: $n = 45$, $R = 0.92$, $R = 0.64$, respectively; Figure S1).

The principal component analysis (PCA) was used to identify the influence certain parameters have on the variation of samples. PC 1, which described 81.05 % of the variation, was strongly influenced by soil parameters in the order N_t > AC > TOC > NMP > pH (Figure 2A).

PC 2, explaining 9.56 % of the variation, was strongly influenced by pH, but the samples clustered along PC 1. The upper 10 cm of the MT treatment were separated from all other samples along PC 1 in the direction of increasing C and N pools (Figure 2A).

3.2 | Compost application

The TOC content was higher in all organic treatments for all sampling years compared to the control and mineral treatment ($p < 0.001$) (Figure 3A).

In 2015, TOC in the organic 525 N treatment was significantly higher than in the organic 175 N treatment; the organic-mineral treatment took an intermediate position ($p < 0.001$). In 2018, TOC in organic

FIGURE 1 Selected soil parameters in different depths (0–100 cm) for all tillage treatments (MT = Minimum tillage, RT = Reduced tillage and CT = Conventional tillage) in 2019. (A) Total organic carbon (TOC), (B) active carbon (AC), (C) total nitrogen (N_t), (D) nitrogen mineralization potential (NMP). Different letters indicate significant differences within one depth (Tukey's post hoc test, $p < 0.05$)

525 N was significantly higher than in organic 175 N and the organic-mineral treatment ($p < 0.001$). TOC in all organic treatments increased significantly over the years until the last sampling year 2018 ($p < 0.001$).

In 2018, AC and TOC showed very similar patterns, with an increase in treatments fertilized with compost (Figure 3A, B) ($p < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, respectively).

N_t was significantly higher in all sampling years in the organic 175 N, organic 525 N and organic-mineral treatment compared to the control and the mineral treatment (Figure 3C) ($p < 0.001$). In 2018, N_t was significantly higher in the organic 525 N variant than in both other organic treatments ($p < 0.001$, $p = 0.001$). No significant development over time was evident in the N_t measurements for all treatments, except for organic 525 N, where an increase over the years was detectable between 2010 and 2018 ($p < 0.001$). NMP was increased in the organic treatments in 2010 and 2012 (Figure 3D) ($p = 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, respectively) compared to the control and mineral treatment. In 2015, NMP was highest in organic 175 N compared to all other treatments except the control ($p < 0.001$). In 2018, both organic treatments (175 N and 525 N) were highest in NMP, followed by organic-mineral, mineral and control ($p < 0.001$). Organic 175 and 525 N were significantly different in NMP compared to the mineral and control treatment in 2018 ($p < 0.001$). NMP increased significantly in all variants, except in organic 525 N, between 2010 and 2015 ($p <$

0.001). For the organic 525 N treatment no significant increase until 2015 was observed. In 2018, all treatments, except organic 525 N, showed significantly lower NMP ($p < 0.001$) compared to the previous year.

3.3 | Crop residue management

TOC increased following crop residue incorporation in Alpevorland ($p < 0.001$), see Figure 4(A), and in Marchfeld ($p < 0.001$, data not shown).

AC was enriched after long-term crop residue incorporation only in Alpevorland, in 2014 and 2018 ($p = 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, respectively) (Figure 4B), but not in Marchfeld.

In Alpevorland (Figure 4C, D) and in Marchfeld, N_t and NMP increased after long-term incorporation of crop residues ($p < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, respectively). In Alpevorland, N_t differed statistically between treatments from 2010 onwards ($p = 0.015$), 24 years after the start of the LTE (Figure 4C), whereas NMP already showed differences between the incorporation and removal of crop residues in 2002 ($p = 0.002$) (Figure 4D). Both N_t and NMP did not change significantly over the course of the years in any treatment at both sites.

NMP correlated negatively ($R = -0.49$, $R = -0.53$) with the C/N ratio in Alpevorland in the removal and incorporation treatments,

FIGURE 2 Principal component analysis (PCA) using standard soil parameters (active carbon [AC], total organic carbon [TOC], nitrogen mineralization potential [NMP], total nitrogen [Nt] and pH) with data of the (a) tillage LTE from 2015 to 2019 in depths 0-30 cm, (b) compost LTE from 2018, (c) crop residue LTE in Alpenvorland from 2018 and 2019, (d) mineral fertilization LTE from 2015 and 2018, different colors show different treatments (a) MT = minimum tillage, RT = reduced tillage, and CT = conventional tillage, (b) control, mineral, organic 175 N, organic-mineral and organic 525 N, (c) incorporation and removal, (d) 12 different stages of N-, P-, K- and Mg-fertilization

respectively ($n = 96$). AC also correlated highly negatively with the C/N ratio in the incorporation treatments in Marchfeld (per variant: $n = 32$, $R = -0.78$; Figure S2).

3.3.1 | Crop residue LTE—temporal changes in 2018 and 2019

No differences in TOC between treatments nor between sampling dates were evident in the seasonal observations in 2018 and 2019 (Figure 4E). AC was higher in soil samples after long-term crop residue incorporation compared to removal in April 2019 (Figure 4F) ($p < 0.001$). Soil samples from removal plots had significantly higher AC values in December 2018 ($p = 0.047$). AC in incorporation

samples decreased significantly from November 2018 to December 2018 and increased significantly from December 2018 to January 2019. AC in both treatments decreased significantly from March 2019 to April 2019. In both variants, AC increased thereafter until June 2019, but only removal samples rose significantly ($p < 0.001$). In summer, no significant differences between treatments were observed.

No differences in N_t between incorporation and removal treatments in the course of these two years were detected and no significant differences between sampling dates were evident (Figure 4G). NMP showed significantly higher values in August and November 2018 and in March 2019 for the incorporation samples (Figure 4H) ($p = 0.019$, $p = 0.014$, $p < 0.001$). Moreover, NMP increased significantly from January 2019 to March 2019 and decreased significantly from March 2019 to

FIGURE 3 Development of selected soil parameters from 2010 to 2018 (19 to 27 years since start of compost application LTE) for all treatments (control, mineral, organic 175 N, organic-mineral, and organic 525 N). (a) Total organic carbon (TOC), (b) active carbon (AC) (only measured in 2018), (c) total nitrogen (N_t), (d) nitrogen mineralization potential (NMP). Different letters indicate significant differences within one sampling year (Tukey's post hoc test, $p < 0.05$)

April 2019 for the incorporation samples ($p < 0.001$). Until summer there was a non-significant increase of NMP in 2018 and 2019 for incorporation and removal treatments ($p = 0.1$, $p = 0.1$, $p = 0.372$, $p = 0.135$, respectively).

Examining the results of the PCA clearly reveals that N_t , NMP, TOC and AC discriminated the two treatments along PC1, which described 54.01% of the variation, into two clusters (Figure 2C). Incorporation treatments clustered in the direction of rising N_t , NMP, TOC and AC levels along PC1, whereas the removal treatments clustered in the opposite direction of PC1. PC1 was influenced in the order $N_t > NMP > TOC > AC$. PC2 described 23.86% of the variation.

3.4 | Mineral fertilization

After long-term mineral fertilization, N_t , NMP and TOC showed no significant treatment differences and no effect of the two sampling years. The PCA, however, revealed that the treatment with very low nitrogen fertilization is separated from all other treatments in the direction of increasing pH (Figure 2D).

4 | DISCUSSIONS

4.1 | Tillage

Minimum and reduced tillage are considered conservation tillage methods because they loosen the soil but do not turn the soil around. Reduced tillage should enhance the carbon and nitrogen content in the upper soil layer and therefore contribute to long-term carbon storage in soils and a balanced and efficient nutrition for the soil flora and fauna (Amelung et al., 2018).

The current study confirmed that TOC and AC increased with decreasing tillage intensity in the upper soil layer as reported in Neugschwandtner et al. (2014) and Awale et al. (2017), respectively. Bongiorno et al. (2019) found increased AC in the top layer of RT, whereas our study detected this only for MT. The spread of RT samples along PC1 compared to MT and CT samples illustrated the intermediate position of RT between MT and CT samples regarding soil C and N pools. The TOC increase in the topsoil under MT can generally be explained by an accumulation of organic material in the topsoil layer in this management variant. This organic material serves as a substrate

FIGURE 4 Development of selected soil parameters from 2002 to 2018 (16 to 32 years since start of crop residue LTE) in Alpenvorland for both treatments (incorporation and removal). (a) Total organic carbon (TOC), (b) active carbon (AC) (only measured in 2014 and 2018), (c) total nitrogen (N_t), (d) nitrogen mineralization potential (NMP). Development of soil parameters in 2018 and 2019 at the crop residue LTE in Alpenvorland for both treatments (incorporation and removal) for (e) total organic carbon (TOC), (f) active carbon (AC), (g) total nitrogen (N_t), (h) nitrogen mineralization potential (NMP). Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments within one sampling year (a–d) or at one date (e–h) (Tukey’s post hoc test, *p* < 0.05). Asterisks indicate significant differences between sampling dates within one treatment [****p* < 0.001, ***p* < 0.01, **p* < 0.05]

for microorganisms, which can boost microbial biomass as reported by Kandeler and Böhm (1996), who investigated the same LTE as in the current study. TOC was more evenly distributed in CT down to a depth of 40 cm, and TOC declined faster when going down the soil profile in reduced tillage intensity. We recorded a very similar pattern for TOC and AC and explain this by the transfer of organic materials into deeper soil layers and good aeration under CT (Bongiorno et al., 2019; Kandeler & Böhm, 1996). Culman et al. (2012) concluded that AC was not superior to other soil C fractions in determining depth differences and temporal dynamics. In contrast, AC in our study had an advantage over TOC in detecting differences between treatments in various depths. This confirms the broadly accepted view that AC is more sensitive to tillage management than TOC (Awale et al., 2017; Bongiorno et al., 2019).

A meta-analysis by Pecio and Jarosz (2016) found increased N_t for noninversion tillage (i.e., RT), but not for no-tillage; the effect was stronger in the upper 10 cm and in depths >30 cm compared to 10–30 cm. In the same experiment as in our study, Kandeler et al. (1999) had shown that microbial parameters such as N mineralization increased under reduced tillage due to the accumulation of organic matter near the soil surface. In a different tillage LTE in the Marchfeld, N_t and NMP increased in the topsoil layer after seven years when tillage intensity was decreased (Neugschwandtner et al., 2014). A Spanish LTE investigating the effect of tillage and liming on microbial N turnover also reported increased N mineralization due to reduced tillage intensity and liming (Vázquez, Benito, Espejo et al., 2019; Vázquez, Benito, Navas et al., 2019). NMP was able to differentiate between CT and RT in the upper 10 cm, whereas N_t was not. Accordingly, Gajda and Przewłoka (2012) found increased NMP in RT and MT compared to CT and therefore differentiated between RT and CT samples. Generally, the increase in NMP can be explained by the enhanced activity of microorganisms involved in N mineralization processes when tillage intensity is reduced and soils become less disturbed (Gajda and Przewłoka, 2012; Vázquez et al., 2017). Regarding the distribution of N_t in different depths, Neugschwandtner et al. (2014) showed a faster N_t decline at greater soil profile depths when tillage intensity was decreased. They also showed a more even distribution of N_t down to 40 cm in CT. Those patterns agree with our results for N_t and NMP and can be explained by the mixing of soil and incorporation of crop residues when CT is applied (Neugschwandtner et al., 2014).

Our findings also coincide with observations by Gajda and Przewłoka (2012) indicating that NMP is more sensitive to different tillage treatments than N_t . Schomberg et al. (2009) identified NMP as a reliable parameter to determine potentially mineralizable N. Those authors designated the parameter as less time consuming and more standardized than the traditional, long-term aerobic incubation method. Nonetheless, they also stress that NMP is somewhat more time consuming than other methods for detecting potentially mineralizable N, such as N mineralized in hot potassium chloride (Schomberg et al., 2009).

Hurisso et al. (2016) proposed that AC more closely reflects the accumulation and stabilization of SOM than C determined by short-

term aerobic incubation of rewetted soils. This is because AC was closely related to management practices known to promote long-term C storage. Moreover, the PCA revealed AC as a very promising parameter indicating SOM dynamics in relation to different tillage practices. Data of the tillage LTE were clustered along PC1, and AC had a greater influence on PC1 than TOC. The enrichment of AC under MT can indicate a high potential to accumulate organic carbon with MT in the topsoil (Hurisso et al., 2016). AC could therefore be used as an early parameter predicting SOC dynamics (Awale et al., 2017). However, making such statements, it must be considered that AC is still a poorly defined pool and can also vary extensively by changing the method procedure (Tirol-Padre & Ladha, 2004; Pulleman et al., 2021; Wade et al., 2020).

For MT and RT, the correlation between AC and NMP was strongly positive. This is reasonable as both parameters describe active soil fractions (Dell, 2009; Drinkwater et al., 1997; Nendel et al., 2019; Tatzber et al., 2015) and correlate with total SOM content as correlations of AC and NMP to TOC and N_t , respectively, were found.

4.2 | Compost application

Soils often face a loss of organic matter content, whereas the production of organic waste by industry and from urban areas is increasing. Recycling those products in agriculture is a promising option for both soil fertility and soil quality (Diacono & Montemurro, 2011).

All organic fertilization treatments showed higher TOC contents in all sampling years compared to the control and mineral treatment. Accordingly, compost application enhanced TOC contents in soils when compared with unfertilized or chemically fertilized soils in Diacono and Montemurro (2011). The positive effect of time on TOC suggests that compost application enhances the SOC content over time, as already reported in Lehtinen et al. (2017).

Several studies found increased AC contents when different types of organic amendments were applied (Benbi et al., 2015; Bongiorno et al., 2019; Li et al., 2018; Mirsky et al., 2008), similar to the current study. Tatzber et al. (2015) already reported that AC increased as a reaction to compost application in the same LTE. AC showed very similar patterns to TOC and therefore cannot provide further information on SOM dynamics in the compost dataset. Regular measurements over time could contribute information on temporal dynamics.

Organic fertilization and the mixture of organic-mineral fertilization increased N_t compared to the control and mineral fertilization in the current study in all sampling years. N_t increased over the years only in the high compost application (organic 525 N). Pecio and Jarosz (2016) found increased N_t contents when compost was applied compared to mineral fertilization at the same plant-available nutrient level. Those authors did not detect any effect of time on N_t following compost application, which agrees with our findings for lower compost application rates but disagrees for the organic 525 N treatment. Note, however, that 525 kg is a very high N application rate that is not frequently applied in practice in Europe; it is nearly the maximum application

amount of compost allowed. NMP was also positively affected by compost application. Comparable to our findings, compost application raised mineral N in 59 European LTEs reported by Pecio and Jarosz (2016). Moreover, the effect of time was much more evident for NMP than for N_t . An increase of NMP until 2015, 24 years after the start of the LTE, was observed in all treatments except for organic 525 N. Unexpectedly, NMP was higher in the control than in all treatments except organic 175 N in 2015. Furthermore, NMP did not increase in the organic 525 N treatment over the years. This can be explained by enhanced N accumulation with increasing compost application (Hadas et al., 1996) leading to N-saturation in soils (Amelung et al., 2018). Moreover, NMP decreased again from 2015 to 2018 in all treatments except organic 525 N. The spring/summer growing season in 2018 was exceptionally hot and dry (Toreti et al., 2019), and dry conditions clearly hamper C and N mineralization (Hueso et al., 2012). This may help explaining why the NMP values in 2018 decreased in almost all treatments. Only the organic 525 N treatment seemed to be more resilient towards the drought stress and maintained the previous year's NMP level. This resilience might have occurred because organic amendments support soil moisture retention and enhance microbial growth and activity (Hueso et al., 2011; Hueso et al., 2012). NMP therefore showed much greater temporal variability than N_t . This suggests NMP to be a more time-dependent property, which is less stable than N_t , an observation which has already been discussed in the literature (Culman et al., 2013; Pecio and Jarosz, 2016; Wander, 2004). This makes NMP sensitive to climatic conditions, which complicates the interpretation of the results but could also provide further details on the reaction of soil processes to changing environmental conditions.

4.3 | Crop residue management

The incorporation of crop residues may be a valuable tool to maintain SOC levels and to improve soil fertility (Lehtinen et al., 2014) because it returns biomass to the soil which is otherwise removed.

TOC increased following long-term crop residue incorporation compared with its removal. This observation was previously described in Spiegel et al. (2018) for the same experiments. No changes of TOC over the years were detected either in Marchfeld or in Alpenvorland, in line with the results of Poeplau et al. (2015). Minasny et al. (2017) stated that TOC can increase when incorporating crop residues as a management practice. Nevertheless, no gradual increase was observed in the current study: TOC fluctuated over the years in Alpenvorland. Moreover, AC increased significantly with crop residue incorporation versus removal in Alpenvorland. This agrees with Chowdhury et al. (2015), who found enhanced amounts of different C fractions, including labile C (determined with 0.1 M NaOH), when crop residues were incorporated rather than removed.

In our study, crop residue incorporation increased N_t significantly compared to plots where such residues were removed. This result is in accordance with Pecio and Jarosz (2016). Moreover, NMP

was increased significantly after incorporating rather than removing crop residues. These findings agree with Charoulis et al. (2005) and O'Connell et al. (2004), who used other parameters to detect N mineralization. NMP was increased after incorporation already in 2002 in Alpenvorland, in contrast to N_t . Hence, NMP could be depicted as an "early detection parameter" of changes in SOM and microbial dynamics due to alternative management practices, as suggested earlier (Kandeler et al., 1999; Pecio & Jarosz, 2016).

AC and NMP correlated positively, but both correlated negatively with the C/N ratio. Such a negative correlation between AC and the C/N ratio of the soil was reported earlier (Bongiorno et al., 2019). Those results indicate that AC and NMP are labile SOM fractions. A low C/N ratio means that there are more easily decomposable compounds in the soil, namely AC and NMP.

4.3.1 | Crop residue LTE—temporal changes in 2018 and 2019

N_t and TOC did not differ between incorporation and removal samples in the course of these 2 years. We did, however, detect significant differences in AC and NMP between the two treatments at different sampling dates and between various sampling dates. Parameters, such as NMP and AC, were reported to be sensitive towards fluctuations during a year (Clark et al., 2019; Culman et al., 2013; Kandeler & Böhm, 1996), mainly influenced by moisture and temperature (Kandeler & Böhm, 1996; McGill et al., 1986;) and crop residue incorporation and its timing (Chowdhury et al. 2015; Cookson et al. 1998).

According to ZAMG (2018), the soil temperature was below 0°C on 16 November for the first time in 2018, and on 30 November 2018 the soil was frozen hard and dry. Such environmental conditions help to understand why AC decreased in both treatments from November to December 2018 because microbial activity is typically reduced at low temperatures (Amelung et al., 2018), and substrates become poorly available for microbes under frozen conditions. In January 2019, AC increased significantly in the incorporation samples and was once again higher than in the removal samples. On 23 January 2019, prolonged snow cover started (ZAMG, 2019). As reported by Brooks et al. (2011), snow cover can enhance biological activity in soil by providing liquid water and based on its temperature-insulating function. The higher biological activity in the soil during that snow cover could explain the increased AC in incorporated samples during that time. The sensitivity to seasonal changes is greater in soils with high SOM (Kuhnert et al., 2012), this could explain why incorporation samples react stronger to seasonal weather changes. Finally, AC dropped significantly in late April 2019, similarly to patterns for NMP. In early May 2019 the soil temperature was below 0°C for the last time of the year (ZAMG, 2019) causing the decrease of AC via reduced microbial activity. AC values increased again for both treatments until June 2019. As explained by Culman et al. (2013), the strong connection of labile C fractions to plant growth and the soil temperature changes at that time could have caused those dynamics. During summer, no significant differences

between treatments were evident. AC was very dependent on seasonal changes and short-term weather dynamics.

In the incorporation treatments, NMP increased significantly from late January 2019 to March 2019 and decreased significantly thereafter in the early summer months. According to ZAMG (2019), the vegetation period in 2019 started on 15 February, which seems to be the reason for the NMP increase until March 2019. Furthermore, the soil temperature was below 0°C in early May 2019 (ZAMG, 2019). As the activity of soil microorganisms drops at low temperatures (Amelung et al., 2018), this could have reduced NMP in incorporation samples until the end of April. Kandeler and Böhm (1996) reported higher NMP in MT compared to CT samples in the topsoil layer in autumn. Similarly, we found significantly higher NMP values in August and November 2018 for incorporation treatments. The topsoil layer in MT and incorporation samples might be comparable because both are enriched in OM (Chowdhury et al., 2015; Kandeler & Böhm, 1996). With the incorporation of crop residues N remains in the soil, which might be lost to a large extent when crop residues are removed (Cookson et al., 1998). The residues, incorporated in autumn, explain why NMP increased during autumn in incorporation samples. Furthermore, in autumn the risk of N leaching is generally higher. Continuous crop residue incorporation, especially with a high C/N ratio, might help retain mineral N in the soil (Cookson et al., 1998).

The temporal dynamics of NMP and AC show a parallel development. The high values of NMP and AC in March 2019 indicate abundant mineralizable substrate. Both fractions declined until late April 2019, demonstrating that most of the easily available substrate was decomposed or not accessible at this time. Culman et al. (2013) also showed that AC and N mineralization exhibited similar temporal dynamics during a growing season. The conclusion is that AC and NMP are more sensitive to short-term temporal dynamics compared to TOC and N_t , as previously described in the literature (Culman et al., 2013; Wander, 2004).

4.4 | Mineral fertilization

The investigated parameters N_t , NMP and TOC did not differ significantly across fertilization treatments and years.

These results are in contrast to other studies, where TOC increased with N fertilization (Alvarez, 2005; Poeplau, Bolinder et al., 2015). Many authors state that the effect of mineral fertilization is only evident when aboveground crop residues are returned to the soil (Alvarez, 2005; Bolinder et al., 2020; Su et al., 2006). Alvarez (2005) attributes the effect of enhanced TOC following mineral fertilization to increased amounts of returned crop residues due to N fertilization. In the current study, crop residues were returned to the soil after harvest from 1991 onwards. Thus, the nonexistent effect of mineral fertilization cannot be explained by the removal of crop residues or the increased amount of above and below ground biomass due to mineral fertilization. Nonetheless, a possible increase of TOC following N fertilization

might be influenced by climate, crop rotation and soil texture (Alvarez, 2005).

Pecio and Jarosz (2016) stated that mineral fertilization affected N_t positively. This is not the case in the current study for N_t and NMP. Importantly, however, the increase in Pecio and Jarosz (2016) was relative to no mineral fertilizer at all, whereas the current study compares different levels of mineral fertilization. Finally, the effect of mineral fertilizer depends on geographic location, sampling depth and duration of the LTEs (Pecio & Jarosz, 2016).

As the PCA revealed, pH was higher at the low nitrogen application rate. This is reasonable and agrees with the literature stating that nitrogen fertilizers can have an acidifying effect (Ghimire et al., 2017).

4.5 | Synthesis of results

The impact of alternative management practices on soil C and N pools as well as the ability of AC, TOC, NMP and N_t to detect treatment effects and influence of time and depth was evaluated in the current study. The impact of tillage on soil C and N was medium-high as the impact was mostly in the upper soil layer. AC was superior to TOC in evaluating treatment effects in different depths. More details about depth distribution of SOC could be very useful in terms of long-term carbon storage in soils (Chenu et al., 2019). NMP was able to differentiate between all the different tillage treatments in the upper soil layer and provided therefore more details than N_t . The effect of compost application on soil C and N was very high. NMP showed temporal dynamics over the years better than N_t . Crop residue incorporation had a medium high impact on soil C and N. TOC showed the effect of the treatments in the long-term stronger than AC. However, NMP can be used as an early detection indicator showing the effect of crop residue incorporation faster than N_t . However, one must be careful with those interpretations as NMP is a very sensitive parameter and might be subject to short-term fluctuations when only sampled once per year. A thought-provoking finding was though that AC and NMP reflected seasonal changes much better when compared with TOC and N_t . As microbial residues might be the main contributor to stable SOM (Miltner et al., 2012) the microbial CUE might play a major role on how much of the carbon can be stabilized, e.g., on clay minerals. Changes of CUE over the year are influenced by temperature, moisture, nutrient availability and the subsequent effect on the microbial community (Qiao et al., 2019; University of Vienna, 2020). Hence, adapting the timing of soil amendments to times of high CUE may be a promising approach to stabilize C in the soil (University of Vienna, 2020). With that regard methods like AC and NMP, reflecting seasonal variations, are highly relevant.

Hence, AC and NMP, reflect labile SOM fractions rather than stabilized ones, which contradicts the suggestions by Hurişso et al. (2016), Tiroi-Padre and Ladha (2004) and Romero et al. (2018). AC and NMP can provide further details on SOM pools and processes related to its decomposition and carbon accumulation in soil compared to TOC and N_t with special regard towards depth distribution and seasonality

of SOM dynamics. Also, the effect of certain management practices was well reflected by AC and NMP. Generally, management practices, such as reduced tillage intensity, compost application and crop residue incorporation, were beneficial to soil C and N pools. The effect of mineral fertilization was neglectable.

5 | CONCLUSION

In the tillage long-term experiment (LTE), AC and NMP were increased in the topsoil layer, and AC values differed in various soil layers, pointing to different SOM processes. Compost application was beneficial for C- and N-pools, and NMP reflected temporal dynamics over several years. Crop residue incorporation increased C- and N-pools, and NMP and AC reflected short-term seasonal dynamics. We have demonstrated that AC and NMP are two valuable, low-cost methods that help characterizing changes in labile C- and N-pools after modification of soil management. Based on long-term field experiments testing soil tillage, different crop residue management and organic/mineral amendments, we recommend these methods to determine the biochemical parameters of C- and N-fractions that characterize the substrate amounts readily available for microbial C- and N-mineralization. These approaches provided additional details on SOM dynamics compared to TOC and N_t , especially when considering different depths and temporal dynamics. AC and NMP measurements show short-term fluctuations better than TOC and N_t . Therefore, it might be reasonable to use AC and NMP to better understand SOM decomposition and stabilization processes throughout a year and in different soil depths. Further, reactions of AC and NMP to management practices could help farmers to tackle changing climatic conditions by using alternative management practices. However, consulting those two methods exclusively and only measured on one sampling date during a year when evaluating long-term carbon storage in soil is questionable and could lead to misinterpretations. Further investigations on the carbon fraction that is determined by AC can help to better understand what AC tells about SOM stabilization processes.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

ORCID

Sophia Hendricks <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7972-6140>

Ellen Kandeler <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2854-0012>

Taru Sandén <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9542-0117>

Eugenio Diaz-Pines <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9935-106X>

Jörg Schneckner <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5160-2701>

Heide Spiegel <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1285-8509>

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